

ULTIMATE STRENGTH OF POSTBUCKLING FOR SIMPLY SUPPORTED
RECTANGULAR COMPOSITE THIN PLATES
UNDER COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

It is proved that the ultimate strength of postbuckling for simply supported rectangular composite thin plates under compression is far higher than their buckling stress through the test of 283 rectangular composite thin laminates in this paper. The ultimate strength of the composite thin plates is studied using large-deflection theory and small-deflection theory of thin plates. According to the failure criterion of the composites, the curve of coefficient C in the formula of the ultimate strength is found finally. It is in accord with the experimental values for the plates having 45 degrees off-axial, and for longitudinal and latitudinal plates, when $\beta < 0.11$, the theoretical values are higher. The coefficient C given in this paper may be referred in product design.

KEYWORDS: Compression; Failure Criterion; Composites; Postbuckling; Ultimate Strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

As is well known, the postbuckling metal plates can be successively subjected to the load. For some metal plate, the ultimate strength can reach thirty times of the buckling stress. In order to study the bearing capacity of the composite plates through the test and theoretical analysis, the failure tests of the 283 specimens of GFRP thin rectangular plates under compression are carried. It is proved that the GFRP plates in postbuckling still have higher bearing capacity. For the tested specimens their ultimate strength are four to twenty-five times of the buckling stress, the majority is higher than ten. It can be seen, the composite plates in postbuckling also have

greater potential bearing capacity. If the design method of the ultimate strength is adopted, then obviously the weight of the space vehicle and aircraft product can be reduced.

In this paper the ultimate strength of the orthotropic composite plates are studied using the large-deflection theory and small-deflection theory, and the theoretical formulae are deduced respectively. The large-deflection theory is combined the strength theory of the composites, and the theoretical values of the ultimate strength are in agreement with the experimental results for the plates with 45 degrees off-axial. For the longitudinal or latitudinal plates, when $\beta < 0.11$, the theoretical values are higher. The result calculated by small-deflection theory is a specific example of the large-deflection theory, and approaches to the minimum value. Therefore, they can be used in product design, and is reliable and safety.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF THE ULTIMATE STRENGTH

For the tested specimens their length a is 200 mm, their width b are 150, 140, 120, 100, 90, 80 mm, etc., their thicknesses t are 0.6 to 1.4 mm. The fixture improved by us is reasonable, to satisfy the assumption of keeping straight longitudinal side and moving freely. The failure forms of the thin plates in compression postbuckling are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 Typical failure forms

Fig. 1 a) and b) are the failure forms of the unimproved test fixture, they are unreasonable. Fig. 1 c) and d) are the failure forms of the improved fixture. The failure form of d) is ideal one. Generally, the process of the failure is that when the load reaches a certain value, the white points (i.e. debonding of the matrix) are occurred at cross-points of the longitudinal and latitudinal fiber which are located at the plate corner. After that, the white points are extend along a certain angle. When the load is again increased, the cracks may be seen and the sound be heard. As the cracks are expanded, the sounds are enhanced, and the load is reduced.

The angle α has following relation with the longitudinal half-wave number m and the dimensions of the plate.

$$\operatorname{tg} \alpha = \frac{a}{mb} \quad (2.1)$$

The tests show that the load at which the white points occur is about 70% of the failure load. The ultimate load of the thin plates is expressed by the form of Von Kármán [1]

$$P_{ult} = C \sqrt{E \sigma_B} t^2 \quad (2.2)$$

where E and σ_B are the elastic modulus and strength in compression, C is the coefficient related with the properties and dimensions of the plate. The experimental results (using improved fixture) are drawn in Fig. 2 and 3. The parameter β in Fig. 2 and 3 is $\sqrt{E/\sigma} t/b$. The solid circulars are experimental points calculated by 45 degrees off-axial properties of composites.

Figure 2 The relation between C in the formula of the ultimate strength and β for rectangular thin plate under longitudinal or latitudinal compression

Figure 3 The relation between C in the formula of the ultimate strength and β for rectangular thin plate under 45 degrees off-axial compression

3. THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE ULTIMATE STRENGTH

The bearing capacity of postbuckling for the rectangular thin plates under compression had been presented by G. Schnadel at first [2]. The formulae of the ultimate strength for the simply supported orthotropic composite rectangular plates are derived using the large-deflection theory and small-deflection theory in following, respectively.

3.1 Large-Deflection Theory The following stress function is adopted

$$\sigma_x = \phi_{,yy}, \quad \sigma_y = \phi_{,xx}, \quad \sigma_{xy} = \phi_{,xy} \quad (3.1)$$

The equilibrium and compatibility equations as follows

$$D_{11} w_{,xxxx} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) w_{,xxyy} + D_{22} w_{,yyyy} + t(\phi_{,yy} w_{,xx} - 2\phi_{,xy} w_{,xy} + \phi_{,xx} w_{,yy}) + q \quad (3.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{E_2} \phi_{'xxxx} + \left(\frac{1}{G} - \frac{2\mu_1}{E_1} \right) \phi_{'xxyy} + \frac{1}{E_1} \phi_{'yyyy} = \\
 & (w_{'xy})^2 - (w_{'xx})(w_{'yy})
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

Boundary conditions are

$$x = 0, a : w = 0, w_{'xx} + \mu_2 w_{'yy} = 0 ;$$

$$y = 0, b : w = 0, w_{'yy} + \mu_1 w_{'xx} = 0 ;$$

In order to solve the stress state of the plates under postbuckling, the following assumptions are given: a. the edge side of the plate keep straight during the process of deformation; b. the plate edge sides may freely move along supporting, and the shear stress is not occurred.

Assuming the buckling surface of the plates is

$$w = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \tag{3.4}$$

To simplify theoretical analysis, only take the first term, assuming

$$w = f \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \tag{3.5}$$

The solution has also been found using the more terms of formula (3.4). The theoretical ultimate strength is reduced by 10% than that of using the equation (3.5). For the plate with $\lambda = 1.3 \sim 2.0$, it is only reduced by about 6%. Substituting the equation (3.5) into equation (3.3), the stress function is obtained by integrating

$$\begin{aligned}
 \phi &= \frac{f^2}{32} \left[E_2 \left(\frac{\lambda}{m} \right)^2 \cos^2 \frac{2m\pi x}{a} + E_1 \left(\frac{m}{\lambda} \right)^2 \cos^2 \frac{2\pi y}{b} \right] \\
 & - \frac{P_x}{2} y^2 - \frac{P_y}{2} x^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

The latter two terms of the formula is the general solution of the equation (3.3). Therefore, the mid-plane stresses in the plate are

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= -E_1 \frac{\pi^2}{8} \left(\frac{mf}{a}\right)^2 \cos \frac{2\pi y}{b} - P_x \\ \sigma_y &= -E_2 \frac{\pi^2}{8} \left(\frac{f}{b}\right)^2 \cos \frac{2\pi x}{a} - P_y \\ \tau_{xy} &= 0\end{aligned}\quad (3.7)$$

According to Bopernoph-Galerkin equation, the average compressive stress P_x may be found

$$P_x = \sigma_{cr} + \frac{\pi^2 f^2}{16b^2} \left[E_1 \left(\frac{m}{\lambda}\right)^2 + E_2 \left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^2 \right] \quad (3.8)$$

where σ_{cr} is buckling stress. Substituting the equation (3.8) into equation (3.7). Using the failure criterion of maximum normal stress, P_x can be found finally

$$P_x = \frac{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^4 \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}}{\left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^4 \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1} + 3} \left(\sigma_B + \frac{2 \sigma_{cr}}{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^4 \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}} \right) \quad (3.9)$$

The ultimate load of the plate is

$$P_{ult} = P_x b t \quad (3.10)$$

We see $m > 2$ from the failure process mentioned above, therefore, the ultimate load of the plate is

$$P_{ult} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\sigma_B + 2 \sigma_{cr} \right) b t \quad (3.11)$$

The ultimate strength of the plate is

$$\sigma_{ult} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\sigma_B + 2 \sigma_{cr} \right) \quad (3.12)$$

3.2 Small-Deflection Theory The stress distribution of postbuckling plate is ununiform. The middle part of the plate is subjected to buckling stress, but the stresses at the edges of the plate are successively increased, and reaches maximum value finally. For this stress state, Von Karman assume that the stress distribution of the plate is shown in Fig 4 b), the stress are concentrated on the two strips of width b_e . Using the

Figure 4

deflection surface as the formula (3.5), the equivalent width of the thin plate can be obtained by the energy method

$$2b_e = t \sqrt{\frac{\pi \sqrt{E_1 E_2} [1 + \mu_2 \sqrt{E_1/E_2} + 2 G_{12} (1 - \mu_1 \mu_2) / \sqrt{E_1 E_2}]}{6 \sigma_B (1 - \mu_1 \mu_2)}} \quad (3.13)$$

Then, the ultimate load of the plate is

$$P_{ult} = 2 b_e t \sigma_B \quad (3.14)$$

For the orthotropic composites thin plate having $E_1 = E_2$, $G_{12} / E_1 = 0.2$, $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 0.15$, then is

$$P_{ult} = 1.59 \sqrt{E \sigma_B} t^2 \quad (3.15)$$

For the composite thin plate having 45 degrees off-axial, when $G_{45} / E_{45} = 0.8$, $\mu_{45} = 0.47$, then the ultimate load is

$$P_{ult} = 2.49 \sqrt{E_{45} \sigma_{45}} t^2 \quad (3.16)$$

As an example of our GFRP specimen, using longitudinal properties, then is

$$P_{ult} = 1.38 \sqrt{E \sigma_B} t^2 \quad (3.17)$$

4. ULTIMATE STRENGTH ACCORDING TO STRENGTH THEORY OF COMPOSITES

From the failure phenomenon, it can be seen that the more ideal failure occurs at plate corners which begin with appearing white points, i.e. the matrix in cross-points of the fiber begin cracking. After that, the damage regions are extended along a certain angle. Finally, the cracks which can be seen by eyes are appeared, at the same time, the larger sound can be

heard. Therefore, it may be considered that the strength of postbuckling for the rectangular composite plates is controlled by the matrix strength as the microscopic strength theory of composites[4]. The matrix in the postbuckling plates is subjected to stress state of triaxial, according to the strength theory of matrix, the ultimate strength of the thin plates under compression can be found. To simplify the analysis, in this paper, the ultimate strength of postbuckling plate is calculated using the energy strength theory of composites. The energy strength theories have several kinds, as Tsai-Hill, Hoffman, Tsai-Wu etc. They are all failure criterion of the second power function, for in-plane stress state, the general expression is [3][5]

$$\{\sigma\}^T \{F\} + \{\sigma\}^T [F] \{\sigma\} = 1 \quad (4.1)$$

where

$$\{\sigma\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \{F\} = \begin{Bmatrix} F_x \\ F_y \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}$$

$$[F] = \begin{bmatrix} F_{xx} & F_{xy} & 0 \\ F_{xy} & F_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & F_{ss} \end{bmatrix}$$

For different strength theory, F_{xx} , F_{yy} , F_{xy} , F_{ss} , F_x , F_y are different. According to the failure phenomenon, the flexural stresses must be considered for stress state of postbuckling plates.

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma'_x &= -\frac{12z}{t^3} [D_{11} w'_{xx} + D_{12} w'_{yy} + 2 D_{16} w'_{xy}] \\ \sigma'_y &= -\frac{12z}{t^3} [D_{12} w'_{xx} + D_{22} w'_{yy} + 2 D_{26} w'_{xy}] \\ \tau'_{xy} &= \frac{12z}{t^3} [D_{16} w'_{xx} + D_{26} w'_{yy} + 2 D_{66} w'_{xy}] \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

Adding to the formula (3.7), then, the stresses in the plate are

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_x &= \sigma_x + \sigma'_x \\ \sigma_y &= \sigma_y + \sigma'_y \\ \tau_{xy} &= \tau_{xy} + \tau'_{xy} \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

According to the formulae (4.1) and (4.3), the coefficient in the formula of the ultimate strength for simply supported rectangular composite thin plate

can be obtained finally. The theoretical results are drawn on Figs. 2 and 3. Fig. 2 shows that for longitudinal or latitudinal plate, when $\beta < 0.11$, the theoretical values are higher. Fig. 3 shows that for the plate with 45 degrees off-axis, the theoretical values are in accord with experimental results.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The formula (3.10) is simplified as the form of the formula (2.2), then the coefficient C is

$$C = \frac{A+B}{\beta} \quad (5.1)$$

where

$$A = \frac{1 + \left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^4 \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}}{3 + \left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^4 \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}}, \quad B = \frac{2 \sigma_{cr}}{\sigma_B \left[3 + \left(\frac{\lambda}{m}\right)^4 \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}\right]}$$

when $m \gg 2$, it is simplified further

$$C = \frac{1}{3\beta} + \frac{2K}{3} \beta \quad (5.2)$$

where K is buckling coefficient of the rectangular plate. For longitudinal and latitudinal specimens are 2.54, for 45 degrees off-axial specimen is 6.2. Let the first derivative of the formula (5.2) with respect to β is equal to zero, then, the smallest value of the coefficient C is got finally. For longitudinal or latitudinal plate, $C_{min} = 1.50$. For 45 degrees off-axial plate, $C_{min} = 2.35$.

When $\sigma_{cr} = \sigma_B$, the corresponding β and C are obtained as follow: longitudinal or latitudinal, $\beta_{cr} = 0.625$, $C_{cr} = 1.59$; 45 degrees off-axis, $\beta_{cr} = 0.401$, $C_{cr} = 2.49$.

It can be seen, assuming $\sigma_{cr} = \sigma_B$, the coefficient obtained by the large-deflection theory is in agreement with that of small-deflection theory.

From researches mentioned above, the following conclusions can be got

1. The improved fixture can be used to test the ultimate strength of post-buckling for rectangular composite thin plates.
2. Using the energy strength theory of the composites, the theoretical half-wave numbers calculated by the large-deflection theory are in accord with experimental results. For the ultimate strength of longitudinal or latitudinal plate, when $\beta < 0.11$, the theoretical values are higher. For

the plates with 45 degrees off-axial, the theoretical values are in agreement with experimental values. When $\beta < 0.06$, the theoretical values are higher slightly.

3. The theoretical value calculated by the small-deflection theory is practical. It is a specific example of the large-deflection theory. The difference between it and the minimum of the large-deflection theory is very small. It can be applied in product design, and is safety and reliable.
4. When β is smaller, the large-deflection theory should consider triaxial stress, the theoretical analysis will be carried on further.

6. REFERENCE

1. T. von Kármán, etc., The strength of thin plates in compression, Trans. ASME, Vol. 54, APM 54-5, (1932).
2. G. Schnadel, Die Ueberschreitung der Knickgrenze bei dunnen patten, Proc. 3d. Intern. Congr. Applied Mechanics, Stockholm, (1939)
3. R. M. Jones, Mechanics of Composite Materials, 1975.
4. Z. Zhou, The Proceeding of 8th National Conference of GFRP/Composites, C-11, (1989).
5. S. W. Tsai, Composites Design, 1986.

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